

THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES FORMATION OF PHARMACY STUDENTS AT ENGLISH LANGUAGE STUDIES

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Abstract: In modern conditions of increasing globalization, the need for the training of highly qualified pharmacy specialists who speak English has become more urgent. For a modern specialist, it is important not only to communicate with foreign partners and patients, but also the ability to use knowledge of English in professional field.

Key words: competencies, IPER, language training, language proficiency, approaches, observation

Introduction

Language proficiency helps effective communication, is a universal means of successful professional activity and self-realization. In connection with the foregoing, the requirements for language training and the level of professional competence of a graduate of the pharmacy faculty of the institute are increasing. However, the IPER currently includes only one general cultural competence related to the study of foreign languages - the ability to communicate in oral and written forms in Uzbek and foreign languages to solve problems of interpersonal and intercultural interaction. Considering that a foreign language will be included in the mandatory national assessment system (CEFR), as well as the growing need for specialists to speak English, there is a contradiction between the modern requirements of society and the requirements of the our standard of higher education.

Modern requirements for the competencies and content of higher education in the study of pharmacy sciences were formulated by G.N. Morozova, A.N. Polosin, A.G. Frolov. The problems of the formation of professionally oriented competencies

in the study of a foreign language are devoted to the works of L.V. Pokushalova, E.V. Fedotkina. I.V. Aleshchanova, N.A. Frolova. In the works of I.A. Evstigneeva considers the problems of the formation of professional competencies through information and communication technologies. The problems of assessing competencies as a set of general cultural and professional competencies are considered by G.I. Ibragimov.

It should be recognized that research in the field of the formation of professional competencies in pharmacy students through the study of English is not enough. The priority task in teaching English is the formation of professional competencies aimed at the practical use of the English language as a tool for realizing professional interests.

As a rule, studies aimed at studying English at a institute pay attention to interaction with people from different countries and cultures. Professionally-oriented teaching of a foreign language at non-linguistic faculties of universities is considered from the point of view of interdisciplinary coordination and intercultural interaction. Based on the theories of the competency-based approach, it should be said that by competencies we mean knowledge, skills and the ability to apply them in various situations. The specificity of the formation of professional competencies in the process of learning English by students of the pharmacy faculty of the institute is that the language acts as a means, and as a tool and basis for the formation of professional competencies. Professional success will not be achieved without English proficiency. Therefore, there is a need not only to select the content of educational material, but also to apply innovative approaches and pedagogical technologies. In this case, it is necessary to use project technology, which is based on didactic principles, procedures for problem-based learning and the activation of students' self-studies.

An analysis of pedagogical experience and real practice shows that the complexity of the formation of professional competencies in the study of English among pharmacy students lies in the fact that students need to form a package of

professional competencies, while taking into account their internal consistency with each other. In the conducted pedagogical research, we applied a variety of methods: analysis of pedagogical practice in the learning process, analysis of the level of language proficiency reading, pronunciation, translation, knowledge of vocabulary by students. The interview pursued the goal of developing an individual route for learning the language and was supposed to identify students' motivation and interest in meaningful texts. The questionnaire was aimed at identifying the level of language proficiency - it was supposed to reveal the ratio of passive and active knowledge of the English language. The analysis of pedagogical experience took into account modern realities and the direction of trends in the professional sphere.

Our survey among 100 students (5 groups) of the pharmacy faculty of the IPER (17–20 years old) showed that students have different levels of language training. It draws attention to the fact that their language training consists in understanding the text, that is, reading and translating an English text, passive command of the language (77% of respondents), and not on pharmacy topics. Of these, 13% answered that they were engaged in exercises aimed at foreign language speech activity, that is, communication, and 10% noted that they had experience in foreign language training - speaking. As noted above, students do not have vocabulary on pharmacy topics. The results of observation, interviews and questionnaires show the main problems that students-future pharmacists face in the process of learning English: the construction of correct speech constructions hinders insufficient vocabulary, the prevalence of skills of passive work with text (reading texts). There is a clear lack of motivation and interest in speaking and listening comprehension.

In this regard, the following tasks are clarified: pay attention to the formation of speech and discursive competencies; to form an English vocabulary on pharmacy topics; make individual routes for mastering the language, in order to awaken the motivation to learn a foreign language.

As a rule, in the educational process, more attention is paid to the communicative function of the English language, aimed at interpersonal and

intercultural interaction in accordance with our standard of higher education. Therefore, the development of language, speech and communicative competencies is limited, as it does not take into account the professional activities of future specialists. In this regard, the task of forming discursive competence arises as the ability to understand the realities of the country under study, as well as the pharmacy diversity and resources of the country, knowledge of essentials of pharmacy and basic studies of leading pharmacists. Discursive competence is the ability to perceive various types of discourses, which allows building a behavior strategy and background context in the process of professional communication. The formation of lexical competence allows you to meaningfully form a vocabulary, fill it with a variety of terms in the framework of professional activities. Based on the experience of conducting classes and taking into account that passive knowledge of the language prevails among students, in our opinion, emphasis should be placed in the classroom and in extracurricular activities on a combination of intensive and extensive reading of thematic texts. The text should attract with a variety of vocabulary and, accordingly, expand the vocabulary of students. The relationship of both the text and the oral situation makes it possible to expand the lexical field, it is easier to use words, and the thematic text allows you to combine lexico-semantic types.

The process of formation of competencies acts in unity and interconnection, in accordance with our standard of higher education. The process of formation of professional competencies in the study of English by students - future pharmacists, acts as an integral characteristic of achieving the main result - the preparation of a highly qualified specialist. The introduction of an integral competence that ensures communication in English in the field of professional discourse and readiness to interact in a professional English-speaking environment will increase the effectiveness of students' language training. Therefore, the introduction of professional competencies, reflecting the integral nature of the formation of competencies in the classroom for the study of the English language, is an urgent need. It should be noted here that for the effective implementation of English-

language communication for students of a natural profile, the need for skills and competencies in understanding speech by ear and speaking is revealed. For successful mastery of English-speaking communication in the field of professional activity, attention should be paid to the formation of speech competencies. The formation of these competencies is most appropriate to carry out in creating an environment of professionally oriented English-speaking communication, which implies a combination of learning English as a means of mastering one's specialty and as a means of expanding professional communication. This necessitates changes in the content of education and the structure of training sessions. It is necessary to shift the emphasis in the content of the thesaurus, increase attention to training on the speech act of students.

An analysis of existing pedagogical practice shows that traditional education does not fully achieve the goal of developing professional competencies. Therefore, the proposed approach makes it possible to obtain more stable results in the teaching and proficiency of the English language by students of the Faculty of Pharmacy for the purpose of professionally oriented use of the language. When organizing training sessions, attention should be paid to the following: types of speech practice should be related to the specifics of the specialty received; verbal interaction should correspond to the set goals, for which it is necessary to organize not only intra-group communication, but also the purposeful performance of independent work by students; focusing on the content of speech, rather than on grammatical rules.

The formation of professional competencies requires the development of listening and speaking skills in English, taking into account professional training and the scope of the language in future professional activities. An analysis of the process of teaching English, the content of educational texts, assignments, exercises, as well as the organization of forms and methods of educational activity, led us to the implementation of a multi-level approach to teaching. This approach implies highlighting the individual route of language acquisition in order to form a positive motivation for language learning. This approach allows you to gradually level the

level of knowledge in the study group, which subsequently opens up the possibility of using various forms of classes, organizing intra-group communication, as well as the practical manifestation of English knowledge in the form of role-playing trainings, presentations, preparing articles and participating in scientific conferences.

The next logical step in improving English language teaching is the organization of independent work, consistent with the learning process. Such pedagogical tactics make it possible to increase the subjectivity of students and develop readiness for professional self-development, awareness of the importance of mastering the English language as a factor in improving professional training. The introduction of effective teaching methods implies that: the subject matter of the texts should reflect the interest of the student and contain professional information, that is, be of an individual nature, which implies the variability of texts and tasks; the content of the classes should reflect familiarity with the pharmacy diversity and resources of the country and individuals, that is, reflect a professionally oriented orientation; the use of phraseological turns, sayings and proverbs in accordance with the professional orientation should serve to achieve automatism in mastering speech structures; drawing up dialogue structures enhances communicative competence; the activation of humanitarian knowledge, manifested in the disclosure of the relationship between the history of science, fiction and the activities of prominent personalities, helps to expand the discourse.

Independent work of students in modern realities is impossible without the use of information and communication technologies (ICT). The main advantages of using ICT are not only increasing students' motivation for the subject being studied, creating approximate conditions for reality, but also an important means of developing competencies; optimization of building individual routes for learning a foreign language. ICT makes it possible to reveal the creative potential and abilities of students, to show a creative approach to solving tasks, allows diversifying activities (project technologies, presentations, webinars, the practice of searching for

the necessary information, etc.), which, in turn, leads to the expansion of integrative opportunities for the formation of professional competencies in unity and interconnection - linguistic, speech, discursive, communicative. The use of ICT in the study of English increases the subjectivity of students and expands the opportunities for self-development and self-reflection. As a result of a survey among students of I-II courses of Pharmacy and industrial pharmacy, 72% of respondents answered that ICT motivates them to learn the language, and allows them to get acquainted additionally with new interesting texts on the subject of their specialty. Therefore, the use of ICT requires a careful selection of tasks and exercises aimed at increasing motivation and subjectivity.

As a result of pedagogical research, shortcomings in the language training of students of the pharmacy faculty of the institute were revealed, which consist in insufficient command of speech, discursive, lexical competence, which in turn causes low motivation in learning English. The specificity of the training of students - future pharmacists is manifested in the fact that they do not have a vocabulary in English in their specialty, in contrast to students of the humanities faculties (historical, philological). The dominant trend is the lack of motivation to master professional vocabulary. In our opinion, as the analysis of pedagogical practice and the results of the study shows, the requirements of our standard of higher education do not reflect the current level of internationalization of life, the mobility of young people. The modern our standard of higher education requires the use of a foreign language only for the purposes of interpersonal and intercultural communication, which narrows the requirements for the competence of bachelors. Therefore, in our opinion, the introduction of additional general professional competence in our standard of higher education is required - "the ability to use knowledge of a foreign language in professional activities".

The conditions for the formation of professional competencies are the alignment of individual professionally-oriented routes for learning the language, leveling the level of training in the study group by organizing intra-group

communication in English. In classroom activities, it is important to expand the vocabulary on professional topics by combining intensive and extensive reading of texts. Extensive reading involves focusing on the correct comprehension of texts. We believe that a combination of intensive and extensive reading is important. Methodologically important is the importance of thematic texts as the basis for expanding the vocabulary and lexico-semantic typology. In real practice, the use of such an approach in appropriate situations helps to enhance and intensify the learning process. The selection of educational content must be constantly improved and updated on the basis of modern pharmacy science data, which also increases the interest and motivation of students. The basis for the formation of professional competencies is design technologies, the implementation of which implies the individual nature of tasks, forms of execution, formatting (definition of boundaries), and testing procedures.

The level of formation of professional competencies among students - future pharmacists is determined by the following indicators: possession of lexical units of a professional orientation; readiness for speech activity, which is manifested in the realization of the potential in foreign language professional communication; ability to use ICT in language learning; readiness for creative self-realization in the framework of professional activities, which indicates the formed motivation for learning English.

Conclusion

Thus, the process of forming professional competencies is not limited to the educational process. Increasing the IPER student's subjectivity and motivation to learn English allows you to launch a mechanism for the continuous formation of professional competencies among students. The introduction of general professional competence in our standard of higher education - "the ability to use knowledge of a foreign language in professional activities" - will allow systematizing and

streamlining the process of forming competencies in English classes and will meet modern realities.

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